

An Empirical Study of Employees' Sense of Fairness, Engagement and Job Performance in Jiangsu Province

Xia Yidong

Abstract

This paper focuses on the relationship among organizational justice, employee engagement, and job performance, with a view to providing useful inspiration to cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. This paper selects eight representative cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province to conduct a questionnaire survey. The research object is the employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. In the empirical analysis, this study mainly uses SPSS20.0 to conduct sample descriptive statistical analysis, reliability analysis, validity analysis, difference analysis of demographic variables, correlation analysis and regression analysis. The results show that in the context of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province, employees' sense of organizational justice has a positive and significant impact on their engagement; Employees' sense of organizational justice has a positive and significant impact on their job performance; Employee engagement also has a positive and significant impact on their job performance. On this basis, the senior managers of cultural and creative enterprises can improve the organizational justice and engagement of employees of cultural and creative enterprises by establishing a salary distribution system and policies, strengthening the employee participation system of cultural and creative enterprises, building barrier free communication channels, improving the engagement evaluation and management system for employees of cultural and creative enterprises, and strengthening the cultural construction of cultural and creative enterprises, And then improve their work performance and achieve organizational goals.

IJSB

Accepted 11 October 2022
Published 12 October 2022
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7187558

Keywords: *Cultural and creative enterprises; Organizational justice; Engagement; Job performance.*

About Author (s)

Xia Yidong, Asia Metropolitan University, Malaysia.

Introduction

With the improvement of living standards, the cultural and creative industries have had an important impact on people's daily life. At the same time, the importance of cultural as well as cultural and creative industries in the development of the economy is becoming increasingly significant (Zhang 2020; Rotundo & Sackett 2022).). With the continuous improvement of the market economic system and the improvement living standards, consumption concepts as well as consumption needs have undergone significant changes, and consumption needs have become more diverse. On the basis of the continuous improvement of the market opening level, the cultural and creative industries demand increasingly growth has had a greater impact on the economy (Tang & Zhao 2018). Creative and cultural industries involve different links in the industrial chain, such as supply, production, and sales. In the process of effectively connecting relevant production factors such as labor productivity, raw materials, machinery and equipment, cultural and creative elements are integrated, and related products are produced and sold. and thus, gain revenue and profit. The development of any industry will establish mutual cooperation between different enterprises, which will have an impact on the operating efficiency of the enterprise development (Rotundo & Sackett 2022). The development of cultural and creative industries includes market structure, market behavior, market performance, etc., and builds a new and complete system. In the cultural and creative industries, the introduction of high-tech products can effectively improve the technical level of the industry. Advanced products can not only provide technical demonstrations and promote the emergence of new creative products, but also promote enterprise development, improve productivity, and achieve product value. Jiangsu Province is located on the southeast coast where the economy is relatively developed (Dai 2019). With the increasingly rich spiritual and cultural life, the demand for cultural products continues to rise, the consumption expenditure of cultural and creative industries increases, and the market share also increases. This has promoted the development of cultural and creative industries in Jiangsu Province to a certain extent. The development of creative industries in Jiangsu ranks among the best in China. For more than ten years, the cultural and creative industries in Jiangsu Province have continued to develop steadily and gradually become one of the pillars of the national economic development. From the perspective of the development scale and competitiveness of cultural and creative industries, Jiangsu Province is at the forefront. By the end of 2017, Jiangsu Province had built 4,843 cultural industry demonstration (experimental) parks and demonstration bases. From the statistics of the first half of 2022, it can be seen that the cultural and related industry enterprises above designated size in Jiangsu Province (termed to as "cultural enterprises") achieved an operating income of 595.76 billion yuan, by increasing of 3.5% compare to the previous year. Its annual growth rate is larger than the national average of 3.2%. The development of the cultural industry presents three characteristics: the production and operation of cultural enterprises are generally stable, the supporting role of new cultural formats is further enhanced, and the development of regional cultural industries is more coordinated. Among them, among the 9 industries of culture and related industries, 2 industries of cultural investment and operation and news information service continued the rapid growth trend in the first quarter. Their revenue has increased by 19.4% and 14.6% over the corresponding period of a year earlier, accordingly. The operating income of the six industries of content creation and production, cultural equipment production, cultural communication channels, cultural auxiliary production and intermediary services, cultural consumption terminal production, and creative design services continued to maintain steady growth. They increased by 6.5%, 5.4%, 3.1%, 2.3%, 2.2%, 0.2% respectively compare to period of the previous year. Affected by the epidemic, the operating income of cultural, entertainment and leisure services, mainly contact and cluster services, reduction of 25.8% in comparison to same period of previous year. The ravages of the new crown pneumonia epidemic have also dealt a

major blow to the cultural as well as creative industries. In the post-epidemic era, how cultural and creative enterprises can help themselves through difficulties is worthy of attention and research. When an enterprise encounters difficulty, the attitude of employees plays a key role. Under the situation of financial difficulties and unsatisfactory employee wages and benefits, how to retain employees and stimulate their dedication and dedication has become an important issue. Dedicated employees are meticulous in their work, keep improving, perform their duties, and contribute to the organization without complaint or regret; A high level of engagement can promote employees' personal potential, knowledge, skills and self-contribution to the fullest. Therefore, a considerable number of senior managers of enterprises have gradually realized the important role of professionalism in the organization. This paper puts the perspective on how the sense of organizational justice promotes employee engagement, thereby improving job performance, and takes employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu as the research object (Rotundo & Sackett 2022).

Problem Statement

Under the new normal, the development of cultural and creative industries in Jiangsu Province shows the following characteristics: the scale of the industry continues to expand, but the growth rate slows down significantly; the industrial foundation is gradually consolidated, but the contribution is low; the scale of cultural enterprises is small, but the market influence Insufficient; the content of cultural production lacks innovation, and is not closely related to local characteristics, etc. (Rotundo & Sackett 2022; Tang & Zhao 2018)). The business activities of enterprises will be affected by many factors in the market environment. The cultural and creative industry in Jiangsu Province is still in the development stage, and the market competitiveness is not strong. Corporations are confronted with an environment that is becoming more and more complex and competitive. The most obvious change is that with the advent of the knowledge economy, the work content and methods of employees have changed a lot, and the corresponding human resource management orientation has also changed from the focus on people's behavior turns to the motivation of their psychology and work motivation (Fan & Miao 2018). According to Hewitt Associates, the authority on involvement investigations for several years, participating employees have an enormous impact on the performance of a company: earnings per employee are \$3,800 more than other corporations; per employee market value is \$18,600 greater than other corporation; and per employee sales volume is \$18,600 above other corporations by \$27,000. A survey of Fortune's 100 Best Employers also reveals that the companies with high engagement scores are transacting 12 percent more than the other firms in the S&P 500. A study by Towers Watson shows corporations with high employee involvement scores experience a 19-percentage point improvement in the operating profit and a 28-component point adjustment in earnings per share. Employee engagement measures the quality and efficiency of work, which measures the quality and efficiency of the employee's work, determining the quality of a company's products or sales. As you can see, employees' engagement closely correlates with a company's survival as well as its growth. Highly engaged employees have resulted in increased customer loyalty and repeat purchase rates, as well as in increased corporate benefits. Zheng (2019) indicates that with a rapid development of both technology a globalization, human resources is certainly one out of the most important resources at a company's core. The HR has become the resource that is the most precious and the most difficult to duplicate. Manpower also became a key component for the implementation of strategies and the obtaining of performance in companies. Engagement is an important part of employee relationship management in an enterprise. We all know that a highly engaged team has outstanding innovation ability, performance contribution, and team stability. However, many companies are finding it increasingly difficult to increase employee engagement, especially among Chinese employees. More and more surveys show that the level

of engagement of Chinese employees is relatively low, which will affect the development of enterprises. Therefore, how to promote the improvement of employee engagement in our country has become an urgent problem to be solved. (Fan & Miao 2018; Rotundo & Sackett 2022)

Research Questions

Based on the above problem statement, this paper proposes the following specific research questions:

R1: Is there a significant relationship between organizational justice and employee engagement?

R2: Is there a significant relationship between organizational justice and job performance?

Therefore, the research objectives proposed in this study are:

1. To explore the significant relationship between organizational justice and employee engagement.
2. To explore the significant relationship between organizational justice and job performance.

Scope of Research

This paper takes cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province as the research object. Through in-depth and systematic research on the theories related to employees' sense of organizational justice, engagement and job performance, it aims to verify the relationship between organizational justice, engagement and job performance of employees in cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province, as well as the intermediary role of engagement between organizational justice and job performance. This paper also expects to propose more targeted management strategies and methods for managers of cultural and creative enterprises, and provide a direction for Chinese cultural and creative enterprises on how to improve employee performance.

Literature Review

Job performance

The research on job performance can be traced back to about a hundred years ago. Although it has a long history, there is no agreement on its concept in the academic community. Generally speaking, there are two categories, namely, the result theory and the behavior theory. The result theory means to equate work performance with the completion, output and results of tasks or goals. Bernardin and Betty (1984) believed that performance should be the result of work, that is, output. The derivation of the behavior theory comes from Bomen and Motowidlo (1997) who believed that work performance should be a behavior structure with multi-dimensional, employable, continuous and organizational goal related characteristics. Murphy (1990) defined performance as a group of behaviors with people in the organization where they work. Han Yi (2006) believes that job performance is a multi-dimensional aggregation of behavior and results. Tang Lili (2020) proposed that employee performance refers to the sum of work content, results and effects of employees in a certain work cycle. Based on the above research, this paper defines job performance as the sum of the behaviors and results that are beneficial to the organization within and outside the responsibilities of individual employees in a certain period of time.

Organizational justice

Organizational justice focuses mostly on how people feel about the fairness of the treatment they receive in their job relationships. In the realm of social science, the investigation of organisational justice has been a topic of significant interest throughout the past three decades. There are a great number of distinct approaches to defining organisational justice, some of

which include the following: Because the discipline of social science based its definition of organisational justice on people's perceptions, this entails that a behaviour will only be regarded as just in an organisation if its members think it to be such. The philosophical understanding of fairness and this particular perception of fairness are two very separate things. In the field of philosophy, fairness must be defined in line with a certain moral philosophy; to put it another way, many moral code systems are accountable for establishing what aspects of society should be considered just (Colquitt et al., 2001). According to the definition provided by Scholl, Cooper, and McKenna (1987), an individual's engagement in the administration of a number of different organisations can be used to characterise that person's sense of organisational justice. [Citation needed] It is a subjective feeling for individual organisations, which are responsible for determining the reasonable distribution of social resources in various organisations and the fairness of various organisational reward and punishment incentive systems. This is because it is the individual organisations' responsibility to decide what constitutes a reasonable distribution of social resources. This is due to the fact that it is the responsibility of each individual organisation to determine what constitutes a fair and equitable allocation of social resources. It wasn't until a somewhat late stage that researchers in China began investigating the country's conception of fairness. According to Li Chaoping and Shi Kan (2003), the term "sense of fairness" refers to an individual's or team's perception of whether or not they are treated fairly within an organisation based on prior research as well as their own findings. This perception is based on an individual's or team's perception of whether or not they are treated fairly within an organisation. According to the findings of Guo Xinyi and Zheng Jingli (2016), one of the perceived evaluations of organisation members evaluating how the organisation treats itself in the workplace is a sense of fairness. According to the findings of these researchers, this is one of the perceived judgments that organisation members have. Geng Wei (2022) proposed that a sense of organisational justice has a certain impact on the enthusiasm of organisational members and also plays a significant role in promoting the flow of personnel within the organisation as an incentive mechanism. This was done in order to promote the flow of personnel within the organisation. In addition, this perception of fairness within the organisation has a certain bearing on the fervour with which the members of the organisation approach their work.

One further way to think about organisational justice is as a two-dimensional notion. On the first level, there is the objective state of organisational justice. On the second level, there is the subjective state of organisational justice. This indicates that organisations are able to accomplish organisational justice by continuously refining and creating a variety of organisational systems, as well as by adopting procedures and metrics that are relevant to those systems. The second level of organisational justice is the sense of organisational justice, which can be thought of as the individual interpretations of how the organisation treats its members fairly by its members. This can be thought of as the sense of fairness that each member receives from the organisation. However, obtaining full and complete organisational fairness can be a difficult task. Because different individuals have different ideas about what makes justice, there is neither a universally accepted benchmark for fairness nor total fairness. This is because of the diversity of people's beliefs of what constitutes justice. This article leans more toward the second level of meaning because, if a fair system is not acknowledged and accepted by employees, then the impact that system has on employee conduct cannot be exercised to its full potential. This article also leans more toward the second level of meaning because of the following reason:

Employee engagement

In the view of Hewitt, the employee engagement means the degree to which employees are willing to stay at the company and work for the company, which is expressed in three areas: ①

Employees constantly compliment their co-workers, their potential co-workers, particularly customers, and believe in the company's use with positive language to characterize their company, co-workers and work in any situation; ② Employee retention. The employees are anxious to stay with the company, strongly desiring to be part of the company and wanting to be part of the group for the long term, rather than just use their current job as a temporary transition; ③ Working hard. Doing one's best to make extra mileage and devote to work that will contribute to the success of the company. Employee engagement is characterized by Schaufeli et al. (2002) as a motivated, enriching, and intact emotional and a cognitive state in relation to work that is energized, dedicated, as well as focused. They further noted that engagement is not a transient state, but a sustained, permeating emotional and a cognitive state not restricted to personal affairs, events, or actions. Schaufeli et al. (2002) defined employee engagement as a work related, positive, fulfilling and complete emotional and cognitive state, characterized by energy, dedication and concentration. They further pointed out that dedication is not a transient state, but a continuous and penetrating emotional and cognitive state, not limited to individual affairs, events or behaviors. With the deepening of foreign scholars' research, domestic scholars' research on engagement is also ongoing. Zeng Hui et al. (2009) pointed out that engagement is the ability of employees to maintain motivation at work and have a lasting and positive mood, including full commitment to work, joy at work and willingness to make corresponding efforts outside of work. Yang Bo (2012) proposed that employee engagement is a psychological state in which employees identify with their work, devote their time and energy to their work, and are willing to develop with the organization. Huang Zhijian (2021) proposed that "dedication" in the traditional sense of China is a virtue, a dedication without conditions, and a spiritual realm of workers advocated by the Chinese nation for nearly five thousand years; While "dedication" in the modern sense of the West emphasizes not the "virtue" or "spirit" of employees, but the planning of personal career and the significance of the job to this planning. They believe that employees will do their best to do their job only when the job meets the personal career planning. In response to the above definition of employee engagement, this paper gives its own definition. Employee engagement refers to the fact that employees are closely connected with their own companies, psychologically identify with their own organizations, and actively work for the organization in terms of behavior. Employee engagement is influenced by various factors such as environment, people and system, and it is an important indicator to measure how much employees put into the organization and their work.

Methodology

Research Design

From the perspective of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province, this paper conducts an in-depth and systematic study on the relevant theories of employees' sense of organizational justice, engagement and job performance, aiming to verify the relationship between organizational justice, engagement and job performance of employees in cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province, and the intermediary role of engagement between organizational justice and job performance. This paper also expects to propose more targeted management strategies and methods for managers of cultural and creative enterprises, and provide a direction for Chinese cultural and creative enterprises on how to improve employee performance. This paper conducts a questionnaire survey on the employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. The selected sample is 400 employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. In the empirical analysis, this study mainly uses SPSS20.0 to conduct sample descriptive statistical analysis, reliability analysis, validity analysis, difference analysis of demographic variables, correlation analysis, regression analysis and the test of the intermediary role of engagement, and finally verify whether the original hypopaper

is true.

Population/Sampling/Unit of Analysis

In this study, the questionnaires are mainly distributed from July to December 2021. At the same time, this study mainly takes the employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province as the research sample, and realizes the sampling of this study with the cooperation of human resources departments and general management departments of cultural and creative enterprises. In the process of questionnaire survey, this research mainly adopts anonymous method to survey the employees of cultural and creative enterprises, and explains the research purpose of this questionnaire in detail, which can effectively improve the rationality and authenticity of the questionnaire. This paper conducts a questionnaire survey on employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. The selected sample is 8 cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province. Each enterprise has issued 50 questionnaires, a total of 400 questionnaires. In the empirical analysis, this study mainly uses SPSS20.0 to conduct sample descriptive statistical analysis, reliability analysis, validity analysis, difference analysis of demographic variables, correlation analysis, regression analysis and the test of the intermediary role of engagement, and finally verify whether the hypopaper is valid. In this study, the questionnaires are mainly distributed from July to December 2021. At the same time, this study mainly takes the employees of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province as the research sample, and realizes the sampling of this study with the cooperation of human resources departments and general management departments of cultural and creative enterprises. In the process of questionnaire survey, this research mainly adopts anonymous method to survey the employees of cultural and creative enterprises, and explains the research purpose of this questionnaire in detail, which can effectively improve the rationality and authenticity of the questionnaire. The questionnaire of this study mainly uses the Likert five level scale, and the representative scores from "very disagree" to "very agree" gradually increase from 1 to 5. The scores listed in the questionnaire are in direct proportion to the organizational justice of employees in cultural and creative enterprises. The detailed items are shown in Table 3-1.

Table3- 1 Jiangsu cultural and creative enterprises employees' sense of organizational justice measurement items

Variable name	Meaning of the title
Distributive justice	1 . Your compensation is fair compared to other employees in the same position at other cultural and creative companies in the same industry 2 . Your compensation is fair compared to employees doing the same job in your organization 3 . Your compensation is fair compared to employees doing different jobs within your organization 4 . Your compensation is fair in relation to your job duties and intensity 5 . Your compensation is fair based on your contribution to the business
Procedural justice	6. Your company has a well-organized appraisal system 7. Your company's employees have the right to participate in the development of appraisal policies 8. All employees in your company are treated equally in the distribution system 9. Your company is more transparent in the implementation of the allocation system 10. Your company respects the majority of employees' ideas in the allocation system
Interactive justice	11. Your leader cares about your attitude and view on the distribution results, and will actively exchange ideas with you 12. You think you have been valued by leaders in the process of work 13. Your leader made an objective and fair evaluation of you 14. Your enterprise has a corresponding appeal mechanism and way for the distribution results 15. Your enterprise can quickly and effectively handle and respond to employee complaints about the distribution results

The scores listed in the questionnaire are in direct proportion to the employee engagement of cultural and creative enterprises. The detailed items are shown in Table 3-2.

Table3- 2 Employee engagement measurement items of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu Province

Variable name	Meaning of the title
Engagement	1. You feel energetic in the process of completing your duties and tasks 2. You feel energetic and confident in your work 3. You want to enter the work state when you get up in the morning 4. You are full of enthusiasm for your work 5. You can have more thoughts and countermeasures in your work 6. You are proud of your work 7. Busy work makes you happy 8. You devote yourself to your work 9. You often lose yourself in your work

Job Performance Scale

This part mainly uses the items compiled by Borman and Motowidlo (1993) as the scale of this study to measure the work performance of employees in cultural and creative enterprises. The scale includes two dimensions: related performance and task performance. Among them, the related performance mainly refers to the related performance scale designed by Yao Lixia (2002), and slightly modified and adjusted on this basis; Task performance refers to the task performance scale designed by Yu Decheng (2004) in the domestic context. Therefore, the reliability and validity of the scale are good. The scale consists of 12 items, including 6 items (1-6 items) on task performance and 6 items (7-12 items) on contextual performance. The questionnaire of this study mainly uses the Likert five level scale, and the representative scores from "very disagree" to "very agree" gradually increase from 1 to 5. The higher the score listed in the questionnaire, the higher the performance of employees in cultural and creative enterprises; On the contrary, it means that their work performance is lower. The detailed items are shown in Table 3-3.

Table3- 3 Work performance measurement items of employees in cultural and creative enterprises

Variable name	Meaning of the title
Contextual performance	1. You have created great achievements for your enterprise 2. You can always complete your duties and tasks within the specified time 3. You are one of the most outstanding employees in the enterprise 4. Your performance always meets the requirements of your leaders 5. You are very satisfied with your work results 6. Your leader is very satisfied with your performance
Task performance	7. In order to complete the work task within the specified time, you occasionally choose to take a break to work 8. In order to help others or improve the overall performance, you always take responsibility 9. In the company, you often cooperate with colleagues around you 10. You will help and encourage employees who encounter difficulties around you 11. You will consider and voluntarily help other employees for the company 12. When your behavior may affect other employees, you will inform them in advance

Reliability analysis of the scale

This study mainly uses Cronbach's α Coefficient was used to analyze the reliability of each scale. Most researchers have shown that when Cronbach's α When the value exceeds 0.7, it indicates that the reliability of the scale is acceptable. In the opinion of Wortzel (1990), Cronbach's α equivalent values ranging from 0.7 to 0.98 indicate that the scales have high reliability. In this

research, SPSS20.0 was utilized to test the reliability of the dimension of organizational justice, engagement and job performance of employees of cultural and creative enterprises in eight representative industries in Jiangsu. The specific test results of each scale are shown in Table 3-4.

Table3- 4 Reliability analysis of the scale

Scale name	Variable	N of Items	Cronbach's a	Cronbach's a
Organizational justice	Distributive justice	5	0.847	
	Procedural fairness	5	0.828	0.929
	Interactive justice	5	0.805	
Engagement	Engagement	9	0.836	0.836
	Task performance	6	0.857	
Job performance				0.922
	Contextual Performance	6	0.878	

The results of the analysis in Table 3-1 show that the overall Cronbach's α value for the organizational equity scale is 0.929, and the Cronbach's α values for its three dimensions are 0.847, 0.828, and 0.805, respectively; the Cronbach's α value for the engagement scale as a whole and its single dimensional engagement is 0.836; the Cronbach's α value for the job performance scale as a whole is 0.922, and the Cronbach's α values for its two dimensions are 0.857 and 0.878, respectively. The Cronbach's α value for the Job Performance Scale as a whole and its two dimensions of dedication were 0.857 and 0.878, respectively. The results of the above analysis indicate that the reliability of the three scales is high.

Validity analysis of the scale

An exploratory factor of analysis was used to validate the effectiveness of the three scales here. First of all, we need to judge whether factor analysis can be carried out for the three scales, and the judgment criteria mainly refer to KMO and Bartlett test. Secondly, the principal component analysis is used to extract the factor with the standard that the characteristic root is greater than 1.

Findings and Discussion

Research Objective 1: The Impact of Organizational Justice on Engagement Analysis

This part mainly uses Pearson coefficient and two-sided test to analyze the correlation between the three dimensions of organizational justice, single dimension of engagement and two dimensions of job performance of employees in eight representative cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu. At the same time, the closeness between variables is measured by the correlation coefficient. However, if the correlation coefficient exceeds 0.9, the two variables may cause collinearity, and the two variables will be deleted accordingly.

Results

The results of the correlation analysis between the three dimensions of organizational justice: distributive justice, procedural justice and interactive justice and engagement. As shown in Table 4-2.

Table4- 1 Related Analysis Results

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Distributive justice	1					
2.Procedural justice	0.765**	1				
3.Interactive justice	0.748**	0.817**	1			
4.Engagement	0.614**	0.610**	0.601**	1		
5.Task performance	0.613**	0.643**	0.639**	0.617**	1	
6.Contextual performance	0.649**	0.705**	0.648**	0.612**	0.783**	1

Table 4-2 shows that the correlation coefficient between distributive justice and engagement is 0.614, that between procedural justice and engagement is 0.610, and that between interactive justice and engagement is 0.601. This result shows that the three dimensions of organizational justice have significant correlation with engagement; the correlation coefficient between distributive justice and task performance is 0.613, that between procedural justice and task performance is 0.643, and that between interactive justice and task performance is 0.639. The correlation coefficient between distributive justice and related performance is 0.649, that between procedural justice and related performance is 0.705, and that between interactive justice and related performance is 0.648. This shows that there is a significant correlation between the three dimensions of organizational justice and the two dimensions of job performance; At the same time, the correlation coefficient between employee engagement and related performance is 0.612, and the correlation coefficient between employee engagement and task performance is 0.617. This result shows that engagement has a significant correlation with contextual performance and task performance. It can be seen that the relationship between variables in this study has been preliminarily supported, which can further test the research hypopaper.

Research Objective 2 : The Impact of Organizational Justice on Job Performance Analysis

Through the analysis conclusion of correlation analysis, we can see that there is a positive correlation between distributive justice, procedural justice and interactive justice and task performance, and they all reach a significant level of 0.01; Distributive justice, procedural justice and interactive justice also have a positive correlation with related performance, reaching a significant level of 0.01. However, the above research conclusions can only explain the correlation between the variables, and can not accurately explain the specific degree of influence between the two variables. Therefore, we still use regression analysis to further test the impact of organizational justice on employee performance.

Results

(1) Regression analysis of organizational justice on job performance

We regard organizational justice as an independent variable and work performance as a dependent variable for regression analysis, and verify the degree of influence between them on this basis. The analysis results are shown in Table 4-8.

Table4- 2 Regression analysis of organizational justice on job performance

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardization coefficient	T value	P	Adj.R ²	F value
	B	Standard error					
(Constant)	0.577	0.149	Beta value	3.875	0.000		311.458
Organizational justice	0.798	0.045	0.747***	17.648	0.000	0.556	

Note: *** P<0.001, ** P<0.01, * P<0.05, N=349

According to Table 4-8, the adjusted R² is 0.556, so the sense of organizational justice explains 55.6% of the variation in work performance. Regression coefficient of organizational justice: B>0, indicating that organizational justice has a positive predictive effect on job performance. The P value of organizational justice is 0.000, indicating that it is significant at 0.001. Therefore, we believe that organizational justice has a positive and significant impact on job performance. This shows that employees' sense of organizational justice is proportional to their job performance. To sum up, it is assumed that H2 is supported.

(2) Regression analysis of organizational justice on task performance

Next, the sense of organizational justice is regarded as an independent variable, and task performance is regarded as a dependent variable for regression analysis to test the impact of organizational justice on task performance. The analysis results are shown in Table 4-9.

Table4- 3 Regression Analysis of Organizational Justice on Task Performance

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardization coefficient	T value	P	Adj.R ²	F value
	B	Standard error					
(Constant)	0.692	0.165	Beta value	4.205	0.000		218.173
Organizational justice	0.738	0.050	0.685***	14.771	0.000	0.467	

Note: *** P<0.001, ** P<0.01, * P<0.05, N=349

According to Table 4-9, the adjusted R² is 0.467, so organizational justice explains 46.7% of the variance in task performance. Regression coefficient of organizational justice: B>0, indicating that organizational justice has a positive predictive effect on task performance. The P value of organizational justice is 0.000, indicating that it is significant at 0.001. Therefore, organizational justice has a positive and significant impact on task performance. This shows that employees' sense of organizational justice is proportional to their task performance.

Adams' classical fairness theory can be used to explain the impact of distributive fairness on job performance. The fairness theory believes that the sense of fairness comes from the comparison with other reference objects, including the past self and the present others. When the ratio of personal current work input to return is greater than or equal to the ratio of the reference object's work input to return and the ratio of personal past work input to return, employees will feel fair. When individuals feel the sense of unfairness, they may have negative behaviors, such as low mood, reduced effort, slacking off and so on, which will reduce work performance. Procedural fairness refers to employees' perception of the fairness of decision-making procedures. When employees think that the distribution process is fair, even if they are not satisfied with the distribution results, their job performance will not necessarily decline significantly. Organ (1990) pointed out that procedural fairness changed the relationship between employees and organizations from economic exchange to social exchange. After hard work, employees will have expectations for the return results of the organization, but such expectations are not stable, vary from person to person, and are affected by the external

environment. At the same time, personal social exchange is not only for material benefits, but also for high-level needs such as respect, belonging and sense of achievement. In the social exchange relationship, organizational procedural fairness can make employees feel more trusted and respected than distributive fairness, thus prompting employees to take some out of role behaviors to help improve performance in addition to completing their own work. Aryee, Chen et al. (2004) believed that organizational justice is helpful to improve task performance and contextual performance. Procedural justice has a significant correlation with task performance, interpersonal facilitation in contextual performance, and job dedication. Zhang Yan et al. (2015) found that fair distribution has a direct positive effect on task performance and organizational citizenship behavior, while procedural fairness enhances employees' sense of psychological security by providing them with a good organizational environment, thereby improving their task performance (Rotundo & Sackett 2022).

Conclusion

This paper examines the relationship between the three aspects of employees' sense of organisational justice, engagement, and job performance in Jiangsu cultural and creative enterprises, as well as the role of engagement as a mediator between organisational justice and job performance. This paper also aims to present more specific management strategies and methodologies for cultural and creative enterprise managers in China, and to provide Chinese cultural and creative firms with guidance on how to increase employee performance. This paper surveys the employees of cultural and creative firms in eight typical Jiangsu Province industries using a questionnaire. 400 employees from eight cultural and creative firms in Jiangsu Province make up the sample. In the empirical analysis, this study primarily employs SPSS20.0 to conduct sample descriptive statistical analysis, reliability analysis, validity analysis, difference analysis of demographic variables, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and the test of the intermediary role of engagement, and to determine if the original hypopaper is valid (Rotundo & Sackett 2022). The findings indicate that in the context of cultural and creative enterprises in Jiangsu, employees' sense of organisational justice has a positive and significant impact on their engagement; Employees' sense of organisational justice has a positive and significant impact on their job performance; Employee engagement also has a positive and significant impact on their job performance; and employee engagement mediates the relationship between their sense of organisational justice and their job performance. On this basis, senior managers of cultural and creative enterprises can improve organisational justice and employee engagement by establishing a salary distribution system and policies, bolstering the employee participation system of cultural and creative enterprises, constructing barrier-free communication channels, and enhancing the engagement evaluation and management system for employees of cultural and creative enterprises (Dai 2019).

References

- Anderson, & R., L. . (1988). staff beliefs and support for a work redesign intervention. *Journal of Management*, 14(3), 493-503.
- Bakker, A. B. , & Schaufeli, W. B. . (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and Engagement: a multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293-315.
- Bakker, A.B. & Demerouti, E. (2007).The job demands-resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3) 309–328.
- Cote, S. , Saks, A. M. , & Zikic, J. . (2006). Trait affect and job search outcomes. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68(2), 233-252.
- Cropanzano, R. , Discorfono S. M. (2007).Organizational Justice. Encyclopedia of Industrial and Organizational Psychology (Volume 2). *Academy of Management*.
- Dai,Q. (2019). *A Study on the Influence of Organizational Justice on Job Satisfaction in J Company*,

Southeast University

- Emerson, R.M. (1972). Exchange Theory, Part I: A Psychological Basis for Social Exchange. & Exchange Theory, Part II: Exchange Relations and Network Structures. In *Sociological Theories in Progress*, Berger, J., Zelditch, M., & Anderson, B. New York: Houghton Mifflin, pp. 38-87.
- Fan, M., Yu, H., & Miao, Y. (2018). A Study on Payroll Incentive to Employee Engagement in Science and Technology Innovation Enterprises -- Based on the moderating effect of performance management. *Educational Modernization*, v.5 (27), 318-322
- Guo, X., & Zheng, J. (2016). Research on the relationship between organizational justice and employee behavior from the perspective of structural validity, *Journal of Southwest Normal University: Natural Science Edition*, 41 (3), 7
- Han, Y., & Liao, J. (2007). Research on the Impact of Performance Separation on Task Performance and Relationship Performance, *Industrial Engineering*, 9 (4), 5
- Koopmans L., Bemaards C., Hildebrandt V., et al. (2012). Development of an individual work performance questionnaire. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 62(1): 6-28.
- Langelaan, S., Bakker, A.B., van Doornen, L.J.P., Schaufeli, W.B. (2006). Burnout and work Engagement: Do individual differences make a difference? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 40 Menguc, B., Auh, S., Fisher, M., & Haddad, A. (2013). To be engaged or not to be engaged: the antecedents and consequences of service employee engagement. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(11), 2163-2170.
- Mwanzia G.. Effects of change on staff performance in organizations. *Effects of change on staff performance in organizations*, 2015(6): 1147-1155.
- Nancy, & R. Lockwood. (2007). Finding and retaining talent: Management challenges for multinational companies in China. *Human Resources* (11X), 4.
- Niehoff, B. P., & Moorman, R. H. (1993). Justice as a mediator of the relationship between methods of monitoring and organizational citizenship behavior. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 36(3), 527-556. (3), 521-532.
- Organ D.W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behaviors: the good soldier syndrome*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books, 147.
- Pateria P. (2015). Role of emotional aptitude on employee's performance. *Global Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(6): 273-289.
- Peng, J., & Wang, X. (2016) Does having a "heart to heart" with your boss make your work better? -- Follow prototype consistency, work engagement and work performance, *Journal of Psychology*, 48 (9): 1151-1162
- Rotundo, M., & Sackett, P. R. (2022). The relative importance of task, citizenship, and counterproductive performance to global ratings of job performance: a policy-capturing approach. *J Appl Psychol*, 87(1), 66-80.
- Saks, A. Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *Journal of managerial psychology*, 2006, 21(7), 600-619.
- Saks, A.M. & Gruman, J.A. (2014). What do we really know about employee Engagement? *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 25, 155-182.
- Salanova, M. & Schaufeli, W.B. (2008). A cross-national study of work Engagement as a mediator between job resources and proactive behavior. *International journal of human resource management*, 19, 116-131.
- Sun, L., Ling, W., Fang, L. (2010). The intermediary role of sense of fairness between moral leadership and employee engagement. *Science and Technology Management Research*, (6): 167-169
- Tang, C., Chen, B., & Zhao, S. (2018). The Impact of Inclusive Leadership on Employee Engagement in the Context of Chinese Culture, *Economic and Management Research*, 39

- (3), 11 Van Scotter, James R., Motowidlo, S. J. . (1996). Interpersonal facilitation and job dedication as separate facets of contextual performance *Journal of Applied Psychology*,81(5):525~531
- Vernon-Wortzel, H. , & Jingtian, W. Z. . (1990). Organization and management in china: 1979-1990 || the people\'s republic of china as an exporter. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 20(1-2), 161-171.
- Wang,D.,&Qian,Z. (2017). Research on the relationship between leader member exchange differences and new generation employee engagement, *Science and Science and Technology Management* (4), 9
- Wang,H. *Research on the relationship between organizational justice, organizational identity and job performance of dispatched workers*, (Doctoral dispersion, Jilin University)
- Wang,H., Li,X.,&Luo,S. (2003). Verification of the two factor performance model of task performance and situational performance, *China Management Science*, 11 (4), 6
- Wang,J. (2015) *The relationship between job characteristics, turnover intention and emotional commitment: the intermediary role of organizational justice*, (Doctoral dispersion, Shaanxi Normal University)
- Xu,Y. (2020). *The impact of job remodeling on job performance* (Doctoral dispersion, Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics)
- Yang,B. (2012). Research on the improvement of employee engagement in Chinese enterprises: based on the perspective of organizational climate, *Capital Economic and Trade Press*
- Yang,L. (2006). Research on the concept of hotel employee satisfaction and engagement *.Financial sector*, (11): 12-13
- Zhang,B. (2013). Research on Organizational Justice in Informal Organizations *Social scientist*, 5: 69-71
- Zhang,H. (2020). Research on Strategies for Improving Employee Engagement in Agriculture related Enterprises, *Rural Economy and Technology*, 31 (3), 2

Cite this article:

Xia Yidong (2022). An Empirical Study of Employees' Sense of Fairness, Engagement and Job Performance in Jiangsu Province. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 14(1), 116-129. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187558>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/2001.pdf>

Published by

